

ANALYTICAL METHOD FOR FOOD SAFETY
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Geno*Listeria* Multiplex: Identification by multiplex real-time PCR of 30 major clonal complexes of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains

EURL Lm

European Union Reference Laboratory for
Listeria monocytogenes
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ANSES Laboratory for Food Safety

European Union Reference Laboratory for *Listeria monocytogenes*

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History of the method

A method can be updated in order to take account of changes.

A change is considered major when it relates to key aspects, the application field or the critical points of the method, which if taken into account could significantly change the scope, the performance or the result of the analytical method. A major change leads to major adaptations. If the method is modified to this extent, it is then revalidated, totally or partially.

A change is considered minor if it provides useful or practical clarifications, reformulates the instructions to make them clearer or more precise, or corrects minor errors. A minor change do not affect the performance characteristics of the methods; it does not require revalidation

The following table summarises the version history of this method.

Version	Nature of the changes (major/minor)	Date	Main changes
V0	Initiale version	17/01/2022	-
V1	Minor change	15/02/2023	<p>Add reporting dye and quencher in table 1 and section 6</p> <p>Interpretation precisions were provided in section 9.1</p> <p>Add the possibility of 15 µL reaction in section 8.1 and 8.2</p> <p>Range of DNA concentration was updated to 1-0.1 ng/µL. It was specified that measurement must be obtained by fluorimetric quantification of double strand DNA</p>
V2	Major change	05/10/2023	<p>Suppression of CC14-ST91-ST360 from the method</p> <p>Modification of the scheme of the method accordingly, addition of CC18 with the FAM dye to the duplex CC8-CC121 which become a triplex CC8-CC18-CC121</p> <p>The numbering of the PCR was changed starting from IIa-5 because PCR IIa-4 (CC14-ST91-CC18) was removed in table 1</p>
	Minor change		<p>The dye of CC18 probe was changed to FAM (due to the modification of the triplex IIa-1) and CC121 to HEX (due to typo error) in table 1</p> <p>Addition of a specific positive control for CC101 in section 5.1 & 8.2</p> <p>The sentence: All controls DNA can be provided by the EURL for <i>Lm</i>, was added to section 5.1</p> <p>The sentence "If the Ct is less than 30, the PCR is systematically redone". Was removed from section 9.1. As it comes in contradiction with the cycle threshold (Ct≤30) establish for the method.</p> <p>Maisons-Alfort laboratory for food safety was replaced by ANSES laboratory for food safety, exact date of publication, mention to EU funding and "French was specified for the national reference laboratory was added in front page.</p>
V3	Minor change	23/10/2023	Reference to French NRL was removed from the front page.
V4	Minor change	19/09/2025	Add Table 5a with recommended master mixes and add two real-time PCR master mixes with issues in table 5b, based on inter-laboratory validation trail results

		<p>Section 5.1: Modification of the positive control. Plasmid “pBluescriptIISK+” was replaced by “pUC57”, and specific DNA control for CC101 was removed.</p> <p>Method DNeasy® Blood & Tissue kit QiaGen was added in section 7.3.</p>
	Major change	<p>Real-time PCR 149_CC2_8862 performs poorly on complex DNA extracts (such as enrichment broth extracts). It has been replaced by a real-time PCR located at a nearby genetic position with similar characteristics, called 149_CC2_8868.</p> <p>Modification of Tables 2, 3, and 6.</p>

Foreword

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Introduction

The “*GenoListeria* multiplex” in house method was developed by the *Salmonella* and *Listeria* Unit (SEL), this version is an adaptation of the ANSES internal method LSA-INS-1493 developed for simplex PCR assays thought high throughput PCR.

The present in house method “*GenoListeria* multiplex” is made of 12 multiplex reactions.

The present in house method was developed by the ANSES Food Safety Laboratory (ANSES LSAI) in 2021-2022 as part of a multi-partner collaborative effort. The SEL unit, within the framework of the activities of the European Union Reference Laboratory for *Listeria monocytogenes* (EURL *Lm*), is the leader of the project. This method was developed in collaboration with the B3PA unit of the ANSES LSAI Boulogne sur Mer location, the National Reference Laboratories (NRLs *Lm*) of the European Union (BE, CH, CY, DE, GR, IT, NL (RIVM and WFSR), PT, SE, SI, and SK) in charge of *L. monocytogenes* typing in their country, the French Institute for Pig and Pork Industry (IFIP) and ADRIA development of Quimper.

The method was published in 2023 in the scientific journal Microbiology Spectrum: <https://zenodo.org/records/10017525>.

The “*GenoListeria* multiplex” includes the molecular serotyping scheme of Vitullo et al. 2013. It identifies 6 genetic markers through 2 triplex PCR reactions (Lmo0737, prs, plcA and Lmo1118, ORF2110, ORF2819) to provide the molecular serotype of the strains.

Following molecular serotyping, the method allows the identification, by real-time PCR, of 30 clonal complexes (CCs) of Multi locus sequence typing (MLST) circulating in food, animals, and environment and responsible for clinical cases in humans in Europe. The 30 CCs are covered by 30 genetic markers part of PCR reactions providing the following identifications: CC1, CC2, CC3, CC4, CC5, CC6, CC7, CC8, CC11-ST451, CC14-ST14-ST206-ST399, CC18, CC19-ST398-802-1308, CC20, CC21, CC26, CC29, CC31, CC37, CC54, CC59, CC77, CC87, CC101, CC121, CC155, CC193, CC199, CC204, and CC224. CC9 identification is provided by Lmo1118 molecular serotype PCR.

The primers and probes were developed both, to be performed as 35 simplex PCR (In house method LSA-INS-1493) or one duplex and 11 triplex PCR in the present method.

Warnings and safety precautions

The user of this method should be familiar with standard laboratory practices. It is the responsibility of the user to establish proper health and safety practices and to ensure compliance with applicable regulations.

It is essential that manipulations conducted in accordance with this method be performed by appropriately trained personnel.

BIOHAZARD

Infection by this bacterium is frequently accompanied by minor digestive problems, including diarrhoea. However, there are serious forms that may affect sensitive populations such as pregnant women, the elderly and the immunocompromised individuals. Operators handling *L. monocytogenes* must therefore work in a Level 2 laboratory.

HAZARDS OF REAGENTS

For all questions, consult safety data sheets (SDS) provided by the provider or producer.

1. Purpose and scope

This method describes the identification, on *L. monocytogenes* bacterial strains, of 30 CCs of MLST and 5 molecular serotypes by real-time PCR through 12 multiplex PCR reactions.

2. Reference documents

- [1] Vitullo, M. *et al.* Real-time PCRs assay for serogrouping *Listeria monocytogenes* and differentiation from other *Listeria* spp. *Mol Cell Probes* 27, 68-70 (2013).
- [2] NF EN ISO 20837 standard: Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs - Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens - Requirements for sample preparation for qualitative detection
- [3] NF EN ISO 22119 standard: Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs - Real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens - General requirements and definitions
- [4] NF EN ISO 20838 standard: Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs - Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens - Requirements for amplification and detection for qualitative methods

3. Terms, acronyms and definitions

Ct	Cycle threshold
dATP	Desoxyadenosine triphosphate
dCTP	Desoxycytidine triphosphate
dGTP	Desoxyguanosine triphosphate
dTTP	Desoxythymidine triphosphate
DNA	Desoxyribonucleic Acid
dNTP	Desoxynucleotide
<i>Lm</i>	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>
pb	base pair
prs gene	Gene coding for phosphoribosylpyrophosphate synthetase
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
plcA	Phosphatidylinositol-phospholipase C
Taq	<i>Thermus aquaticus</i>

4. Principle of the method

The 35 Geno*Listeria* genomic markers scheme (Table 2) are identified by Taqman® real-time PCR probes. Two PCR protocols were optimized, one conventional thermal cycling and one fast thermal cycling (Needing dedicated master mix and thermocycler). The real-time PCR assay identify a genetic marker specific of the 30 CCs and 5 molecular serotypes sought by the method. Among the 35 real-time PCR probes of the Geno*Listeria* scheme, 29 were designed within the framework of the method development by the ANSES SEL unit. The real-time PCR assay also integrate the 6 markers of the molecular serotyping scheme of Vitullo et al. 2013 that identify the strain molecular serotype (so called serogroup) IIa, IIb, IIc, IVb et IVa and L through two triplex PCR reactions. The PCR that identify the genus *Listeria* (*prs* – gene of the phosphoribosylpyrophosphate synthetase) and a species *monocytogenes* (*plcA* – gene of the Phosphatidylinositol-phospholipase C) of Vitullo et al. 2013 scheme are used as internal control. Both PCR are part of the same triplex. The Vitullo et al. 2013 scheme was developed by the UK-NRL *Lm*, Public Health England. This method details the implementation of 12 multiplex PCRs (adapted for use of conventional real time PCR instruments). The molecular serotype should be performed in a first stage, the CC multiplex identification should be performed according to the molecular serotype. In this method (Figure 1), the CC are given by order of abundance according to three studies that described the diversity of *Lm* in Food in France (Maury et al. 2016, Félix et al. 2018) and in Europe (Painset et al. 2019) (Figure 1).

This method requires the following steps:

- Verification of the concentration and quality of the DNA extracts
- Real-time PCR analysis
- Interpretation of results

5. Reagents

Caution: Certain trade names or suppliers may be mentioned by name in the description of the products necessary for applying this method. This information is given as an indication for users of the method and does not in any way imply that ANSES recommends the exclusive use of these products. Equivalent products may be used if it has been demonstrated that they produce the same results.

5.1 Positive control

The reference DNAs used as PCR positive controls for each of the markers come from strains in the ANSES collection, except for two strains that come from the Hungarian NRL and Slovak NRL collections (Table 1). The 39 amplification products derived from the genome of the reference strains, flanked at each end by a 20 bp region, were cloned into six puc57 plasmids. The plasmids carry between five and nine amplification products and are organized as follows (Table 7):

- Plasmid DNA IIa A: CC8-CC121-CC18, CC31-CC37-CC155, CC7-CC14-ST14-CC204
- Plasmid DNA IIa B: CC20-CC21-CC101, CC26-CC29-CC193, CC199-CC11-ST451-CC19-ST398
- Plasmid DNA IIb: CC3-CC87-CC5, CC59-CC77-CC224

- Plasmid DNA_IVb: CC1-CC2-CC6, CC4-CC54
- Plasmid Molecular_serotyping: prs-plca-lmo0737, ORF2819-ORF2110-lmo1118

These plasmid vectors were produced in large quantities and aliquoted. The recombinant bacteria carrying the vector are stored in the SEL unit collection and will not be replated once stored, as the initial plasmid production is so large. These plasmids were mixed at a concentration of 300,000 plasmids per microliter (equivalent to the number of copies present in a suspension of *Lm* genomes at 1 ng/μL). This mixture of recombinant plasmids allows the in vitro controls to be performed in a single analysis.

Table 1: reference ADN

Reference ANSES de la souche	Référence initiale de la souche hors ANSES	Serotype moléculaire	Complexe clonal de Multi locus sequence typing	Sequence type de Multi locus sequence typing
17SEL1LM		IVb	CC1	ST1
17SEL376LM		IVb	CC2	ST2
10CEB88LM		IIb	CC3	ST3
17SEL543LM		IVb	CC4	ST4
16SEL667LM		IIb	CC5	ST5
17SEL82LM		IVb	CC6	ST6
16SEL17LM		IIa	CC7	ST691
17SEL12LM		IIa	CC8	ST8
17SEL375LM		IIc	CC9	ST622
19SEL868LM		IIa	CC11	ST451
18SEL159LM	8916 (LNR SK)	IIa	CC14	ST14
17SEL4LM		IIa	CC18	ST18
21SEL232LM	164 (LNR HU)	IIa	CC19	ST398
08CEB286LM		IIa	CC20	ST20
17SEL88LM		IIa	CC21	ST21
09CEB411LM		IIa	CC26	ST26
17SEL50LM		IIa	CC29	ST849
17SEL370LM		IIa	CC31	ST31
17SEL105LM		IIa	CC37	ST37
18SEL92LM		IIa	CC37	ST37
19SEL881LM		IVb	CC54	ST54
17SEL517LM		IIb	CC59	ST59
09CEB593LM		IIb	CC77	ST77
17SEL107LM		IIb	CC87	ST87
03EB425LM		IIa	CC101	ST775
17SEL63LM		IIa	CC121	ST121
17SEL412LM		IIa	CC155	ST155
11CEB245LM		IIa	CC193	ST193
20SEL79LM		IIa	CC199	ST199
17SEL510LM		IIa	CC204	ST204
10CEB615LM		IIb	CC224	ST224

5.2 PCR reagents

- Taqman primers and probes (Table 2).
- Molecular grade water DNase and RNase free.
- Master-mix for real time PCR (Conventional or Fast) compatible with the method. An optimization is required to implement a never tested master mix. Some master mixes were previously tested by partner laboratories showed PCR issues and are listed for information in table 6a and 6b.

Table 2: Primers and probes for the detection of *GenoListeria* targeted genes

Multiplex	Primers and probes	Probe sequence (5'-3')	Forward primer sequence (5'-3')	Reverse primer sequence (5'-3')	Reference
1	prs	FAM-CATGACAACCACGGATACTTTCTCAATGTTAATTTG-BBQ	CAGGRTTACTCGTTGATTGAATAAC	GCTGAAGAGATTGCGAAAGAAG	Vitullo <i>et al.</i> 2013
1	plcA	HEX-TCAAGATGACTACAATGGTCCGAGTGTA AAA-BBQ	CGGCGCACCTAACCAAGTAA	CAGTCTGGACAATCTCTTTGAATTTT	Vitullo <i>et al.</i> 2013
1	Lmo0737	Cy5-CCAACACTTTCTCATCAATACCATCTTCCC-BBQ	GCATCTTGTTTAGCAAGTGGATC	GAGCACGGAAGTTGCTAGGT	Vitullo <i>et al.</i> 2013
2	Lmo1118	FAM-CCTTTATCTCTCCTGAGTGATACGCCTC-BBQ	CTTAGTATCCAGGATTTAAGACC	CCAAAGAACCAAATTGATCGAATC	Vitullo <i>et al.</i> 2013
2	ORF2110	HEX-TCTCCGTCATTTGTTACCGTTCCCAAC-BBQ	CACTAATCTCATCGACTATAAACTC	TGCACAAGCAGCAGAGGAAG	Vitullo <i>et al.</i> 2013
2	ORF2819	Cy5-CTCGTAAGATCGATATACGTCATGGCAGTTTCC-BBQ	ATCACTAAAGCCTCCATTGAG	GGAAGATTTCCACGCAATACTC	Vitullo <i>et al.</i> 2013
IVb-1	149_CC1_1911	Cy5-TTCCAGCACTCAATGCAATCGC-BBQ	GTTTCGATAGTGTCATAGGA	GCTCTCTATTCAATATTGGTAA	-
IVb-1	149_CC2_8868	FAM-CTTGCCAAACATCCTAAGTTATCGACT-BBQ	TGCACCTGAATTCTAGTTTAC	TGTCCCTTATTCAATCTCTC	-
IIb-1	4711_CC3_6907	Cy5-AGTCGCTTTGACGAATATCAAACCTCAC-BBQ	ACCCAAATAGATCAAAGC	CGGATTCTCTCTATTCTTG	-
IVb-2	4711_CC4_3572	FAM-TGCCTCCTACCAACTGACTGAAG-BBQ	CATCGTAGCCTTTTCATC	GGAACCTAACCGAGGATTA	-
IIb-1	4711_CC5_9574	HEX-AGACACATTAATTTCCGCTTGGCAA-BBQ	CCTTGCTAGCTTCTGTAG	GAAGGTACTTTTACAGACAAA	-
IVb-1	149_CC6_4418	HEX-AACGGATTCTATTAACACGCAAGCAA-BBQ	GGCAGTGTTTGATACATG	CTGGTAGAATAGATTACTTTAGAC	-
IIa-3	258_CC7_6968	Cy5-AACTGCAACTCCAGAGTCAACATAAT-BBQ	GGTGAATATGAGTAAATGGA	GAACCTATATTTTGGGCATTA	-
IIa-1	258_CC8_952	Cy5-AGTCACAGAAACTTCTAAGCCGG-BBQ	GGTACGGGTAGTTTTGTTA	GCCTTTTCAATGAAGTGAA	-
IIa-6	111_CC451_9204	FAM-TTAAGACTCGCGCATGTTGCTGTGCAC-BBQ	GATGGGAGTTAATGATTTATGGATA	ACACCTATTCTTTCTTGATTATACAG	-
IIa-3	258_SNP_LMO002932_ST14	FAM-TCAGGACAAATCAGTGCATTTGGCC-BBQ	GATGCAACTGCTATTAGG	GTTTCGTACATTCGCTTAG	-
IIa-1	258_CC18_7946	FAM-TCTAACTCCTCTGTGTAAGAAGCAATT-BBQ	GTCACATTGGTTATATTTCAAG	CAGGTTTTATTTCACTAGTTTG	-
IIa-6	111-Lmo01705_ST398_1	HEX-CGTAGTTTATCAATACGTCGCAACTTTAGC-BBQ	CTTGCTTCCGCTGATATCAATG	GTCCCAAACACGGTCAGAAA	-
IIa-4	21322_CC20_1143	Cy5-TCTAGCCTGTTCAATTTCTTGATTGG-BBQ	TGTCCTAATAGTGAAGCA	CGTGAAAATGAACAATAAA	-
IIa-4	21322_CC21_5690	FAM-TCAACTTTGCTTGTTTTAAACCAAGA-BBQ	GCAACTAAAATAACTATCTCAA	GGATGAAAATTAAGTATGAAG	-
IIa-5	3511_CC26_4338	Cy5-AGACATAATGAATCATGGACGCTTCTT-BBQ	ACACGACGTATGACTTTA	CAGCATCTTCAAACAGAG	-

Multiplex	Primers and probes	Probe sequence (5'-3')	Forward primer sequence (5'-3')	Reverse primer sequence (5'-3')	Reference
Ila-5	3511_CC29_2081	FAM-TTGACGCTGAACTTGCTAATGC-BBQ	AACGGCTATTAACGGAG	GGCAAAGTTACTACAGTTG	-
Ila-2	1610_CC31_8696	Cy5-ATGAAACGAGCTAAATCTCCTCAATT-BBQ	GAGTGTATGGCATATGAAAG	GATCGTTGATAGAGAATTAATC	-
Ila-2	1610_CC37_4509	FAM-TCAGGCAGCACTTCATAATCCA-BBQ	CCAGAGAATGGCTAGATA	GAACCAATAGAAGAATTGATAC	-
IVb-2	1_CC54_731	HEX-AGCCTCCCGTACCGTAAACCGGT-BBQ	AGGACATATTAGATGTTGTTCTG	GCTTCACCAACACTTAGCATA	-
IIb-2	359_CC59_5912	Cy5-AAAGAATCTCCGACGAAACGCT-BBQ	CAGCAAAAGACAGCAGATA	AGCCAGAATAAATAAATTTACTTAC	-
IIb-2	359_CC77_3146	FAM-ACAGAACCAATTCCTCCAACCA-BBQ	CACGAATCAAACGTGAA	CTTCGCAGGCATTTTATC	-
IIb-1	258_CC87_8655	FAM-ATCCTTTGAGTGATAAACATCGCCTAC-BBQ	GTGACACCATGTAATCTC	GCAGAAAACCTTGAATGA	-
Ila-4	21322_SNP_LMO00485_CC101	HEX-CACTCTTAATGTTATGTGTAAGCCG-BBQ	ATGGCACTTGAATTATTCA	GCCATACGTTGATTTTAC	-
Ila-1	258_CC121_3159	HEX-TTAGATTGCTACTACCGCCAATT-BBQ	ATGGCTACTGAATATATCCC	TCGGAATTTATCATTATATGTTCTA	-
Ila-2	1610_CC155_5334	HEX-ATATTCAGAATCCATCCCTATTTGCG-BBQ	GTCAGAGTCGAATTCATTA	TCTGGAATTTCAAAGTATTG	-
Ila-5	3511_CC193_5118	HEX-TGATGAGGAACCATATCATTCCAATG-BBQ	CTGTCATGTGTTATCCTTG	TGGGAATAACGAGTCAATA	-
Ila-6	111_CC199_711	Cy5-AGACTCTCCACTCCAGCAAACGCTTCTGT-BBQ	CGGAGCATTCACTATATCATTTACA	GTCAGTTGGATGTTAGACAAA	-
Ila-3	258_CC204_2959	HEX-TGTGGACAACCTTCTCTAATTTCTATCT-BBQ	CCTCTTGGTACTTCTAAATTATC	CAGAGCCGAAGATTATCC	-
IIb-2	359_CC224_7283	HEX-TCTTGTCCAAATGTTTCACTATTATCGTAAGTA-BBQ	GAACGTATCTCTAGTAGC	GAAGGATTTATTAGAAATGAAAGTA	-

Figure 1: GenoListeria multiplex scheme

6. Equipment and materials

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Usual microbiology apparatus and equipment

- Freezer $\leq -18^{\circ}\text{C}$
- Microtubes up to 1.5 mL with safety caps (that do not burst open at high temperatures)
- Vortex shaker
- Centrifuge at approximately 5000 RCF
- 96 wells Microplate (200 μL) compatible with the thermocycler and optical sealing film
- Set of micropipettes and tips
- Thermocycler with a rising and falling temperature gradient of $2^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{s}$ for convention thermal cycling or 3 to $5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{s}$ for fast thermal cycling suitable to detect FAM 520 nm, VIC 554 nm and Cy5 669 nm reporting dye and corresponding quencher (Black Berry Quencher™ for instance as proposed by the authors).

7. Samples

7.1 Conditions for acceptance of samples

Genomic DNA must be extracted according to a high quality extraction procedure. No extraction method is recommended, however three methods have been tested during the method validation:

- Extraction of isopropanol/ethanol genomic DNA using the Wizard® Genomic DNA Purification Kit Promega extraction kit (ANSES LSA-INS-1227 operating mode)
- Extraction of genomic DNA on silica column DNeasy® Blood & Tissue kit QiaGen (ANSES LSA-INS-1494 operating mode).
- Extraction of genomic DNA by simple cell lysis InstaGene Matrix® Bio-Rad (ANSES LSA-INS-1526 operating mode).

For these three methods, the DNA concentration must be tested by fluorometric quantification (Qubit see procedure ANSES LSA-INS-1227). A minimum concentration of 0.1 ng/ μL is a prerequisite for the analysis of samples.

7.2 Conservation of samples before analysis

Genomic DNA samples can be stored at a temperature below $5^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a closed 1.5 μL microtube if used within 48 hours after extraction. Otherwise they will be kept, following the same packaging, at a temperature below -18°C for long-term storage.

7.3 Conservation of samples after analysis

The genomic DNA samples can be stored after analysis in a DNA bank for later use, notably for the sequencing of the complete genome of the strains (valid if the extraction was carried out following the Wizard® Genomic DNA Purification Kit Promega extraction (ANSES LSA-INS-1227 procedure) or DNeasy® Blood & Tissue kit QiaGen (ANSES LSA-INS-1494 operating mode).

7.4 Preparation of samples for analysis

The genomic DNA extracts are aliquoted and diluted with DNase and RNase free molecular biology water to bring them to a DNA concentration between 1 and 0.1 ng/μL, before being added to the PCR mix. DNA concentration should be obtained by fluorometric measurement for the only quantification of double strand DNA.

8. Procedure

8.1 Real time PCR analysis in the form of triplex/duplex PCRs

This method requires to use conventional real time PCR instruments with three detection channels: dye FAM 520 nm, dye HEX 554 nm (compatible with VIC 549 nm), dye Cy5 669 nm. In this analysis configuration the PCRs are performed as triplex FAM-HEX-Cy5 or duplex FAM-HEX. The triplex mixes all have the same composition, as well as the duplex mixes. The reaction volume could be performed in 15 μL and 20 μL format.

The PCR should be performed in two rounds:

- 1) For all samples triplex PCR 1 (prs, plcA, Lmo0737) and PCR 2 (ORF2819, ORF2110, Lmo1118).
- 2) The other triplex or duplex PCR (Table 2) may be performed according to the molecular serotype deduced (Figure 1). Multiplex PCR can be performed one by one or several PCRs can be performed at the same time.

8.2 Preparation of the PCR mix

In the mix PCR room

Sample preparation should be adapted according to the PCR mix used.

Triplex			Duplex		
Reagent	20 μ L μ l /reaction	15 μ L μ l /reaction	Reagent	20 μ L μ l /reaction	15 μ L μ l /reaction
H2O	5.3	3.975	H2O	6.2	4.65
2X master mix	10	7.5	2X master mix	10	7.5
20 μ M Forward Primer 1	0.3	0.225	20 μ M Forward Primer 1	0.3	0.225
20 μ M Reverse Primer 1	0.3	0.225	20 μ M Reverse Primer 1	0.3	0.225
20 μ M Probe 1	0.3	0.225	20 μ M Probe 1	0.3	0.225
20 μ M Forward Primer 2	0.3	0.225	20 μ M Forward Primer 2	0.3	0.225
20 μ M Reverse Primer 2	0.3	0.225	20 μ M Reverse Primer 2	0.3	0.225
20 μ M Probe 2	0.3	0.225	20 μ M Probe 2	0.3	0.225
20 μ M Forward Primer 3	0.3	0.225	Total	18	13.5
20 μ M Reverse Primer 3	0.3	0.225			
20 μ M Probe 3	0.3	0.225			
Total	18	13.5			

In a DNA room

According to the plate plan, add 2 μ l of each diluted DNA if the final volume of reaction is 20 μ L, or 1.5 μ l if the final volume is 15 μ L.

Controls: For each duplex or triplex PCR, include:

- the positive control at 1X concentration (mixture of plasmids) (Section 5.1)
- the negative PCR control: DNA-free water (section 5.2).

8.3 Amplification conditions

Conventional program

2 min	50°C	40 cycles
10 min	95°C	
15 sec	95°C	
1 min	60°C	

Temperature ramping 2°C/sec

Fast program*

2min	95°C	40 cycles
3 sec	95°C	
30 sec	60°C	

Temperature ramping 3 to 5 °C/sec

*Fast Program was tested with only GoTaq® Probe qPCR Master Mix (ref Promega A6102)

9. Results

9.1 Control of the validity of the results

An amplification, to be considered positive, must have a detection threshold less than or equal to 30 cycles ($Ct \leq 30$). Late amplifications, beyond 30 cycles ($Ct > 30$), are considered as non-specific.

The positive control and the negative control must have the expected result to validate the manipulation (5.1 and 8.1.1). The internal PCR control prs is positive for the *L. monocytogenes*, *L. innocua*, *L. welshimeri*, *L. seeligeri*, *L. ivanovii*, *L. marthii* and *L. grayi* strains (Vitulo et al. 2013). The PCR internal control plcA is positive for all *L. monocytogenes* strains.

The amplification curve of the test samples, to be considered positive, must be within a detection intensity range greater or equivalent to the positive control (ΔRN): PCR controls (5.1) and internal controls prs and plcA (8.1.1). This control should be applied particularly to the real time PCR 21322_SNP_LMO00485_CC101.

Internal controls (prs and plcA), must be positive for all *L. monocytogenes*. To be valid, the test PCRs must have a Ct equivalent to the internal controls (prs and plcA). If the test PCR Ct is higher than the internal controls, it is necessarily related to contamination.

9.2 Calculation and expression of results

The interpretation of the sample results is carried out by comparison with the control DNA according to table 4. The Geno*Listeria* PCR has been developed so that a strain can only be identified by one of the PCRs performed. If a strain is identified by several PCRs, contamination by several different DNA extracts must be suspected.

It is possible that a strain with a different ST or CC from the target CCs may be identified by some of the PCRs in the Geno*Listeria* scheme. These joint identifications could not be avoided when designing the probes. They are considered as cross reactions. A list of the cross reactions identified during the development of the method is detailed in table 5. The cross reactions must be specified when writing the analysis report.

The interpretation of the results is done according to the table 3 and 4 for the expression of results.

Table 3: Expression of the results

Clonal Complex GenoListeria	CC1	CC2	CC3	CC4	CC5	CC6	CC7	CC8	CC9	CC11 (ST451)	CC14 (ST14-ST206-ST398)	CC18	CC19 (ST398)	CC20	CC21	CC26	CC29	CC31	CC37	CC54	CC59	CC77	CC87	CC101	CC121	CC155	CC193	CC199	CC204	CC224	Other CCs*	Listeria not Listeria monocytogenes**	« Non- Listeria »***		
CC1-P-F-R (149_CC1_1911)	■																																		
CC2-P-F-R (149_CC2_8868)		■																																	
CC3-P-F-R (4711_CC3_6907)			■																																
CC4-P-F-R (4711_CC4_3572)				■																															
CC5-P-F-R (4711_CC5_9574)					■																														
CC6-P-F-R (149_CC6_4418)						■																													
CC7-P-F-R (258_CC7_6968)							■																												
CC8-P-F-R (258_CC8_952)								■																											
CC9-P-F-R (258_CC9_5506)									■																										
CC11-ST451_1_P-F-R (111_CC451_9204)										■																									
CC14-ST14-P-F-R (258_SNP_LMO002932_ST14)											■																								
CC18-P-F-R (258_CC18_7946)												■																							
CC19-ST398-P-F-R (111_Lmo01705_ST398_1)													■																						
CC20-P-F-R (21322_CC20_1143)														■																					
CC21-P-F-R (21322_CC21_5690)															■																				
CC26-P-F-R (3511_CC26_4338)																■																			
CC29-P-F-R (3511_CC29_2081)																	■																		
CC31-P-F-R (1615_CC31_8696)																		■																	
CC37-P-F-R (1615_CC37_4509)																			■																
CC54-P-F-R (1_CC54_731)																				■															
CC59-P-F-R (359_CC59_5912)																					■														
CC77-P-F-R (359_CC77_3146)																						■													
CC87-P-F-R (258_CC87_8655)																							■												
CC101-P-F-R (21322_SNP_LMO00485_CC101)																								■											
CC121-P-F-R (258_CC121_3159)																									■										
CC155-P-F-R (1615_CC155_5334)																										■									
CC193-P-F-R (3511_CC193_5118)																											■								
CC199_2-P-F-R (111_CC199_711)																													■						
CC204-P-F-R (258_CC204_2959)																															■				
CC224-P-F-R (359_CC224_7283)																																■			
plcA	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
prs	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■

■ Positive PCR reaction Cts30

*: Includes all *L. monocytogenes* not targeted by GenoListeria .

** : includes the following specie *L. grayi*, *L. marthii*, *L. innocua*, *L. welshimeri*, *L. seeligeri*, *L. innocua*, *L. seeligeri*, *L. ivanovii*

***: includes bacterial strains not belonging to the family Listeriaceae except for the following species: *L. booria*, *L. newyorkensis*, *L. riparia*, *L. grandensis*, *L. weihenstephanensis*, *L. weihenstephanensis*, *L. rocourtaie*, *L. aquatica*, *L. floridensis*, *L. Fleischmannii subsp. Fleischmannii*, *L. fleischmannii subsp. Coloradonensis*.

Table 4: Molecular serotype interpretation

Molecular serotype (Doumith et al. 2010 nomenclature)	Lmo0737	Lmo1118	ORF2110	ORF2819	plca	prs
IIa						
IIb						
IIc						
IVb						
IVb (atypical)						
IVa						
L						

Table 5: STs or CCs of the strains that can be detected by the PCR of GenoListeria scheme

CC or ST targeted by the method	Real time PCR probe reference	Joint detection of strains not belonging to the targeted CCs – (co-detection predicted <i>in silico</i>)
CC1	149_CC1_1911	ST213, CC183, ST773 (CC373*, ST1125)
CC2	149_CC2_8868	
CC3	4711_CC3_6907	CC1000 (CC489, ST558, ST1046, ST1041, CC1211)
CC4	4711_CC4_3572	(ST631)
CC5	4711_CC5_9574	
CC6	149_CC6_4418	
CC7	258_CC7_6968	(CC373*)
CC8	258_CC8_952	ST1110 (ST1018)
CC9	Lmo1118	(ST184, ST395, ST1331*)
CC11-ST451	111_CC451_9204	
CC14-ST14-ST206-ST399	258_SNP_LMO002932_ST14	CC689 (ST843)
CC18	258_CC18_7946	
CC19-ST398-802-1308	111_Lmo01705_ST398_1	(CC1127)
CC20	21322_CC20_1143	ST19, ST173 (ST226*, ST364, ST378, ST1021, ST1071, ST1078)
CC21	21322_CC21_5690	CC403
CC26	3511_CC26_4338	(ST376, ST790, CC912, ST1024, ST1331)
CC29	3511_CC29_2081	(CC344, ST1082)
CC31	1615_CC31_8696	
CC37	1615_CC37_4509	CC321 (ST648, ST828, ST1068)
CC54	1_CC54_731	
CC59	359_CC59_5912	
CC77	359_CC77_3146	
CC87	258_CC87_8655	CC88
CC101	21322_SNP_LMO00485_CC101	(CC90, ST671, ST1127)
CC121	258_CC121_3159	CC689
CC155	1615_CC155_5334	
CC193	3511_CC193_5118	CC124 (ST798)
CC199	111_CC199_711	(CC739, ST1331*)
CC204	258_CC204_2959	(ST798)
CC224	359_CC224_7283	ST581, ST585 (ST226*, ST1118)

*: ST or CC identified as a cross-reaction by two distinct primer and probe sets

() : ST or CC under brackets were predicted *in silico* as cross reaction, but not tested on strain

Table 6a: Recommended PCR Master Mix

Master Mix	Manufacturer	Thermal cycling
PerfeCTa qPCR ToughMix Low ROX	Quantabio	Conventional
SsoAdvanced Universal Probes Supermix	Bio-Rad	
GoTaq Probe qPCR master mix	Promega	Fast

Table 6b: Master Mix with PCR issues

Master Mix	Manufacturer	Thermal cycling
Taqman Universal PCR master mix	Life technologies	Conventional
Lightcycler 480 Probes master	Roche	
Platinum Quantitative PCR SuperMix UDG	Invitrogen-ThermoFisher	
Luna® Universal Probe qPCR Master Mix	New England Biolabs	
Universal TaqMan Multiplex MasterMix	Thermofisher	Fast
Kapa probe fast qPCR Kit Master Mix (2X) Universal	Kapa Biosystems	

Table 7: Positive control plasmids composition

Real time PCR name	ANSES strain reference	Molecular serotype	MLST Clonal complex	MLST type	Amplicon size	Recombinant plasmid reference	Sequence used as positive control (amplicons flanked by 20 bp at each end)
prs	17SEL375LM	IIc	CC9	ST622	141	Molecular_serotyping	taaattctaactcgtaactagctgaagagattgcgaagaagtaggtattgagttaggaaatcaagtggtactcatttagtgatggagaaatc caaattaacattgaagaaagtatccgtggtgcatgtatatgtttattcaatcaacgagtaactcgtaaaccagaathtaaggaa
plcA	17SEL375LM	IIc	CC9	ST622	79	Molecular_serotyping	cgcttggaagcttgataagcagctggaacatctctttgaaatgtttcacactcggaccattgtagtcatctgtaactggttaggtgctgcgc cgaactgcatgccgaattgcg
Lmo0737	17SEL375LM	IIc	CC9	ST622	102	Molecular_serotyping	tatcattgaaacaacaaacgagcacggaagttgctaggtaacgatgtcttaatttcgctggaaaatgggaagattgattgatgagaaagt gtggggcgatccactgtcaaacaaagatgcaaaagaagtgattaagcaat
ORF2110	17SEL82LM	IVb	CC6	ST6	94	Molecular_serotyping	ttattaggtggaggaattgtgacacagcagcagaggaagcccaatcgatgaaagatagttgggaaacggtaacaaatgacggagaa gagtttatagtcgatgagattgattagaagattgtaattca
ORF2819	10CEB88LM	IIb	CC3	ST3	134	Molecular_serotyping	aagtcaacaatccagtaacatcactaaagcctccattgagctctcgttaagatcgatatacgtcagtcagttccaggactcactgtcatt ctttctctctccgtatattgtggaggagttttggagattgctggtgaaatctccggtgaaaagtagtattat
149_CC1_1911	17SEL1LM	IVb	CC1	ST1	100	DNA-IVb	gatgtgcaaatcttcaggggctgtagtgcagtaggagaaataaactaaatcgattgattgagtgctgaaataaggttattgaga taaattaccaatattgaaatagagagctagaagcgttaaatgatgag
149_CC2_8868	17SEL376LM	IVb	CC2	ST2	109	DNA-IVb	ataaaaaacaagccagattgtcccttattcaatctctcttcaatttcaatttcaatggtgatagaatagtcgataacttaggattgtggca agttttctgtaactagaattcaagtgcatcataatctgctaacatc
4711_CC3_6907	10CEB88LM	IIb	CC3	ST3	119	DNA-IIb	tttctattcttttgcaaaaccaaatagatcaaaagcattactataatagtcgcttgacgaatacaaaactcacaaatcttctgtaactcattttatt cataggtattttatatactcaagaatagagagaatccgtccatgctatttgcctgag
4711_CC4_3572	17SEL543LM	IVb	CC4	ST4	129	DNA-IVb	attctctgtattccttatacctgtagcctttcatcatattgctcctaccaactgactgaagattggcaggaggggccacctattactaaatc aatattagaatacctcaatctcatgattatcaataatcctcggtagtccgttatactacaathtaacaat
4711_CC5_9574	16SEL667LM	IIb	CC5	ST5	99	DNA-IIb	aagtctaataaattgagaatccttctgtagcttctgtagatataaattactaaagacacattaattccgctggcaaaagctgtaggcgctgc tagttgtctgtaaaagctcagaaactaatatttctcgg
149_CC6_4418	17SEL82LM	IVb	CC6	ST6	127	DNA-IVb	aggaatgcaccatataccccggcagtggttatacattggaacggattctataaacacgcaagcaaatagcaatattcattgtagtattca attcttattaaacattctccactgtttgctaaagtaactatttaccagcatttttctgtaataac
258_CC7_6968	16SEL17LM	IIa	CC7	ST691	138	DNA-IIa-A	tctcataaactgctgtagaacctataatttgaggcattataactgcaactccagagtcacaataatcgtactgtgaagttgggtccgaatgg gccagtgattattttgctacctcactagagaagtagaaatcatttactcatattcaacttttcaattgttcaaaaat
258_CC8_952	17SEL12LM	IIa	CC8	ST8	117	DNA-IIa-A	tatgagatccttaggatattgtagcgggtgattttgtaaaagtcacagaactcgaagcgggaagttttctcatgtaatgacataatattcttg attcctaaaaagtcaggaacttctcattgaaaggtcattgatttaaatcattc

Lmo1118, 258_CC9_5506	17SEL375LM	IIc	CC9	ST622	170	Molecular_serotyping	agtttaagattctgttccttagtattccaggatgtaagaccctacctttatcttctcctgagtgatagcctcataatgaaaaagcatcctct tcactgttataagcattcaattgagagagatttttgaaggagtgacatttcatttttgattcgcataattgggtcttggtaaaaaactaa
111_CC451_9204	20SEL24LMLM	IIa	CC11	ST451	167	DNA-IIa-B	tctattgcataaagattaagatgggagttaatgattttatggataatgtaagactcgcgcattgtgctgtgcacaagttcatcttggtttaaa aatgaaatgattggagaataactattacagaatgggacaataaaaaattgattgatctctgtataatcaagaagaatagggttttaag
258_SNP_LMO002932_ST14	17SEL22LM	IIa	CC14	ST91	132	DNA-IIa-A	gaaaatagagtaaaacaacgatgcaactgctattaggaaaaatgatcaggacaaactcagtcattggccatcacggcaggctctacacc taagcgaatgtacgaactattagtggaagaatgaaa
258_CC18_7946	17SEL4LM	IIa	CC18	ST18	148	DNA-IIa-A	gtgcttagattgtaattcaagtacattgggtatattcaagttcagacaaaaactcacattcagtgctcaactacagaagttcgaggctcagatt attgattctataaggaataaattgctctacacagaggagtagataaacaactagtgaaataaacctgtatcagttacaatccagaa
111-Lmo01705_CC19-ST398_1	21SEL232LM	IIa	CC19	ST398	134	DNA-IIa-B	ctggatcattttagaatgcttctcctcgctgatataatgactcacgtgcaaatgaaactttcggcgttattatcaatcgtcgaactttagct acggccgaagatgaatggcatgacaaattgccaagttctgaccgtgttgggacgaattaatgaaacaaatgg
21322_CC20_1143	08CEB286LM	IIa	CC20	ST20	121	DNA-IIa-B	tttttctgtcttttctgttcttaagtagtaagcaaatcttagcctgttcaatttctgattggataaacatttttaagcaggaacgtttcaca gtaaaaatatactaaattcttagtttctcatttcacgaatgatctccaagaaaa
21322_CC21_5690	17SEL88LM	IIa	CC21	ST21	111	DNA-IIa-B	aatctgctcttcatcactgcaactaaaataactatcactctttattataaaaatcaacttctgttttaaaccaagataatcaaatctaa ctcaccaaaaactcatcagtaatttcatccataactctctcttatt
3511_CC26_4338	09CEB411LM	IIa	CC26	ST26	131	DNA-IIa-B	tttgacgttattaagaaaacacgcgatgactttaaatacagacataatgaatcaggacgtcttataaaattttgtctaaaagaataaagaa gcaaaacaaactaaatatacaacaaactacgactctgttgaagatgctgtggaacaactaaacttaca
3511_CC29_2081	17SEL50LM	IIa	CC29	ST849	114	DNA-IIa-B	ttcaaaaacggaactcaaaaacggctataaacggagatattgacgctgaacttctaatgactatttaccaaaaaggattcgtactcga ctgattctataatatttccaactgtagtaactttggcagatgattatattcatcct
1610_CC31_8696	17SEL370LM	IIa	CC31	ST31	148	DNA-IIa-A	ctgggtaacagaatgatcggagtgatggcatatgaaagtttcatcttattcattttatgaaatcctaataacaaatgtaagccaaactttat tttaaaaagcaattgaggagattagctcgttcttttataaagatttattctctatcaacgatccatccatcaatctcactc
1610_CC37_4509	17SEL105LM	IIa	CC37	ST37	114	DNA-IIa-A	tgatgtagcagaaaaagaagccagagaatggctagataactcaggcagcactcataatccagatcagattgcaggaggaagcagatat aattgggtgatgggtgataaaggatcaattcttattgttcccaatggaaatagaaattg
1_CC54_731	19SEL881LM	IVb	CC54	ST54	102	DNA-IVb	ttgggaacagcgaatgtagggacatattagatgtcgttctggagcgtgactataaacatctggattcagggtgatatacgggtttacggtagc ggaggctatgtaagttggggaagcattatctatgaagaggatg
359_CC59_5912	17SEL517LM	IIb	CC59	ST59	123	DNA-IIb	gtatgttaagaaactgatcagcaaaagacagcagataaaatttttaaaaagaatcctccagcaaacgcttcaattcctatagattacaagaa tgaaaaattgtgtgtcagaaaaagtaagtaaaattttattctggcttctgattcgcctattgat
359_CC77_3146	09CEB593LM	IIb	CC77	ST77	141	DNA-IIb	ttgatgtggatgaaaaaccagaaactggaactatcaggatcgttgacagaaccaattcctcaaccaaagaagggtacaatc attgggtgatgatgcaaaaacaaactgaactaagtggaattcaacattgataaaaatgctcgaagaatcactttatacgcgca
258_CC87_8655	17SEL107LM	IIb	CC87	ST87	124	DNA-IIb	ttcttgaaccgaaataggggtgacacctgtaattctcgttgcgaaatcctttgagtgataaacatcgcctactcgaagggtgaaatgaaa ttcccgcatgctccaacacataatttaataatcattccaagtttctgcatagcttttaaccaatcagc
21322_SNP_LMO00485_CC101	03EB425LM	IIa	CC101	ST775	100	DNA-IIa-B	aatgtggtctccaaaagaatggcactgtaatttcaaaccattgttatgaaagaactagttggacgcggttagcacaataacattaagatg gtaaacgtaaaatcgaactgtgctccagaactcgggacgtat

258_CC121_3159	17SEL63LM	Ila	CC121	ST121	146	DNA-Ila-A	cagcaaaactggccaattatatggctactgaatataatccccatataatcaaggctatgatggaaaaatgttacacattttggatattacagcttctaaaattggcggtagtagcaatcaaaaaaatagtacatacagctagaacataatgataaattccgagttaatggtttttaattc
1610_CC155_5334	17SEL412LM	Ila	CC155	ST155	133	DNA-Ila-A	agataggtgtaccaaaagtgtcagagtcgaattcattaaaaaggcaaaagcaaaatcacatcaactctaaaattgttgattattctcagtcactgaaaatttagcgcaaatagggatggattctgaatattcaactttgaaaattccagattcagaaaatgaaatga
3511_CC193_5118	11CEB245LM	Ila	CC193	ST193	133	DNA-Ila-B	agaaaaaccctgtcatgtttatccttgacaggggttttgatgaggaaccatatacttccaatgaaatcaaacattttacagtagaaaaacattgattatcggattcccattcatgttatattgactcgttattccactcaaccgtagctgggtgcttactcgaat
111_CC199_711	20SEL79LM	Ila	CC199	ST199	193	DNA-Ila-B	aatgagtataatgaattttcggagcattcactatatacttacaagcatgattaatctagactctccactccagcaaacgcttctgtataattcagaccgattcctcattaaaattgtcttagtggtcggacaatattttcgcgcgtagaattatgtgatactattgaattcatcatattttgtctc
258_CC204_2959	17SEL510LM	Ila	CC204	ST204	101	DNA-Ila-A	actcaaaatctcatttgatcctcttggtactctaaattatcattcttatcaatctcaaatgtggacaacttctctaatttctcaataaaaataacattgggataatctcggctctgattcctaactcaacatatt
359_CC224_7283	10CEB615LM	Ilb	CC224	ST224	106	DNA-Ilb	tcaaagaaaagtcaaatagagaaggatttattagaatgaaagtagtaaatattttaagatttacttacgataatagtgaaacaattggacaa gataggtattcagctactagagagatcgtcaaaaattcaatcttaaaaa

10. Performance characteristics of the method

The method was validated on extensive 89 strains validation panel (3 strains per PCR target). The real time PCRs were previously validated on a larger panel according to the LSA-PG-0062 method validation process according to the NF EN ISO 16140 standard. The criteria and results of this validation are available in the method validation file "VM/SEL-TM/2019/01".